

JOB SATISFACTION OF BANK EMPLOYEES WITH REFERENCE TO PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS IN SIRKALI TOWN

Dr. S. Soundaranayaki

Asst. Prof. of Commerce, A.V.C College (Auto), Mannampandal, Mayiladuhurai.

Abstract:

Job satisfaction is playing a significant role in every organisation. It is the feeling an employees for doing a particular job. Job expectations differ from person to person. Some individuals may be interested in challenging jobs while others may be interested in routine work. Still, there are some factors that may be prepared to do any work for the sake of monetary benefits. Performance is vital role for job satisfaction. Only those who have the ability will be able to perform. Therefore, the present study is to focus analyse the job satisfaction of employees in private sector banks in Sirkali Town.

Key word : *Employees, Private bank, Job Satisfaction.*

Introduction

Job satisfaction is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings with which employees view their work. It is a worker's sense of achievements and success and is generally perceived to be directly linked to productivity as well as to personal wellbeing. The happier people are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be. A Job satisfaction implies doing a job one enjoys, doing it well, and being suitably rewarded for one's efforts. Job satisfactions can be influenced by a variety of factors, e.g., the quality of one's relationship with their supervisor, the quality of the physical environment in which they work, degree of fulfillment in their work etc., job satisfaction further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work job satisfactions; describes how satisfied an individual is with his or her job.

CONCEPT OF JOB SATISFACTION

- ❖ Job satisfaction is the degree to which individuals feel positively or negatively about their jobs. It is an attitude or emotional response to work task as well as to the physical and social of the work.
- ❖ Job satisfaction can be defined as the positive feeling about one's job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. A person with high level of job satisfaction holds positive feeling about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied holds negative feeling about the job.
- ❖ Robert dictionary of Industrial Relation defines job satisfaction as " those outward or inner manifestations which give the individuals a sense of accomplishment or enjoyment in the performance of his /her work"

CONSEQUENCES OF JOB SATISFACTION

Lack of job satisfaction may lead to the following consequences;

- It may increase the rate of labour – turnover
- It may lead to poor job performance.

- There may be an increase in complaints and grievances.
- Conflicts in the workplace may also increase
- It may give scope for strikes and lock-outs.
- It may disturb stability.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

One of the key factors of any organisation is its employees. The success or failure of the organisation largely depends upon on their satisfaction and dissatisfaction. One of the reasons for deteriorating conditions in an organisation is low job satisfaction. Due to which, work slows down, employees remain absent and sometimes employees may leave the organisation also. High job satisfaction on the other hand, is desired by the management because it tends to be connected with the positive outcomes that managers want. Therefore, the present study is undertaken to analyze the job satisfaction of private sector bank employees in Sirkali Town.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study has focuses the following main objectives:

1. To understand the job satisfaction of private sector bank employees.
2. To suggest measure to improve the job satisfaction of employees in private sector Banks.

METHODOLOGY

This study is mainly based on primary and secondary data. The primary data can be collected from a well designed questionnaire instrument is used to measuring job satisfaction of bank employees of private sector banks in Sirkali Town. The sampling population of the study was selected by 50 employees of private sectors banks in Sirkali Town by applying simple random sampling method. Otherwise, the secondary data can be collected from the various journals, magazines, books and online sources.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study is subject to following limitations:

- The study will be restricted to only private sector banks like, ICICI, HDFC, CUB, KVB, LVB and AXIS BANK employees in Sirkali Town..
- This study is undertaken with regard to job satisfaction of private sector bank employees in Sirkali Town only.

CHAPTER SCHEMES

The presentation of this study is divided into five chapters:

1. The first chapter deals with introduction of the study.
2. The second chapter describes the profile of the study area.
3. The third chapter contains various factors determining the job satisfaction of bank employees.
4. The fourth chapter analyzes the job satisfaction of private sector bank employees.
5. The final chapter conclude that the findings, suggestions and conclusion.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table .1

Sex Wise Analysis

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Male	34	68
2.	Female	16	32
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table shows that, 68% of the employees are male and 32% of employees are female.

Table .2

Relationship with Employees and Supervisor

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Cordial	40	82.66
2.	Moderate	5	8
3.	Not Cordial	5	9.34
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 82.66% of employees feel that the relationship with supervisor is cordial, 9.34% of employees say that relationship between employee and supervisor is not cordial, and 8% of employees reported as relationship with supervisor is moderate.

Table .3

Level of Satisfaction on Target related Incentives

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Satisfied	35	69.33
2.	High Satisfied	11	22.67
3.	Neutral	4	8
4.	Not Satisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, we infer that 69.33% of employees say that target on related incentives is satisfied, 22.67% of employees feel that the level of satisfaction is relating to incentives is highly satisfied, and 8% of employees opined that level of satisfaction on target related incentives is neutral one. No one employees coming under the category of not satisfied.

Table .4**Employee opinion about promotional opportunities**

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Very Good	09	17.33
2.	Good	15	29.34
3.	Average	20	40
4.	Poor	06	13.33
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates that, 75 personnel of the sample banks, 40% of employees feel that the promotional opportunities is average, 29.34% of employees say that the promotional opportunities is good, 17.33% of employees opinion about promotional opportunities is very good, and the remaining 13.33% of employees reported that the promotional opportunities is poor.

Table. 5**Employees Satisfied with Working hours**

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Satisfied	31	61.33
2.	Dissatisfied	19	38.67
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates that, 61.33% of employees feel that the working hours of the sample bank employees is highly satisfied, and 38.67% of employees say that the working hours of the sample banks are dissatisfied one.

Table. 6**Views asked in Decision making**

S.No.	Particulars	No. Of Employees	Percentage
1.	Yes	14	28
2.	No	36	72
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, we conclude that 72% of employees reported as if the bank does not ask any views in bank employees for decision making, 28% of employees feel that if the bank asks the views in bank employees for decision making as a result the employee gets higher job satisfaction.

FINDINGS

The following are the major findings of the study.

- ❖ It was observed that 82% of employees say that the relationship between employees and superior is cordial one.

- ❖ It is clearly shows that 69.33% of employee's opinion that, level of satisfaction is mainly based on incentives provided by the bank.
- ❖ Majority 40% of employees feel that, the promotional opportunities of bank employees is average of the sample banks.
- ❖ It shows that the 61% of employees feel that, the bank working hours is satisfied one.
- ❖ Majority 74% of employees say that, the banks do not arrange the welfare measures to the bank employees.

SUGGESTIONS

The following suggestions may be adopted to have a higher level of job satisfaction among the bank employees.

- To maintain the Conducive working environment of the sample banks.
- To improve the Cordial relationship between the employees and superior.
- Better inter personal relationship.
- Provision of suitable promotion opportunities.
- The private sector banks to conduct the training development programme among the bank employees.
- The private sector banks to provide the suitable incentives and social security benefits of bank employees.
- Job rotations where desirable among the bank employees.
- To Encouraging employee's participations in decision making.

CONCLUSION

The productivity of the work force is the most important factor as the success of an organisation. To achieve high productivity and to reduce the employee's turnover and absenteeism the employees should be satisfied. It should be ensured that they are satisfied, as the success of the organisation depends on the job satisfaction of its employees. The way of achieving is by promoting job satisfaction of the bank employees.

REFERENCES:

- Internet Banking, MC Graw hill Company. Parameshwaran. R and Natarajan. S
- Indian Banking, Sultan chant and Co. Ltd
- Banking and Financial System, Santhanam. B Margham publications.
- Share Commerce Report 2003 Banking Law practice. Versheny P.N. Mita P.K. Indian Financial system
- Banking law practice in india- tannan.s, orient law house, new delhi
- Banking law and practice -p. saravanavel, v. gopal, p.jaganathan, k.t.kandasa, margham publication, Chennai
- Banking law and practice -kalkundrikar, kembhavi, natraj, himalaya publishing house, Bombay
- Indian banking R. parameswaran, s. natarajan, s. chand & co. ltd.,

- Natarajan .s parameshwaran .r - Indian banking s. chand & co. ram nagar, New Delhi 1999
- Nakkiran .s — agricultural financing and rural banking in india, rainbow publications, Coimbatore 1980
- Santhanam .b- balancing and financial system. Margham publications chennai.
- Mathur .B.S- co- operation in India, sahithyabhawan, agra.
- Banking theory law and practice,Garden and Arunkumar,Himalaya publishing house (2006).
- Electronic Commerce Kalarota and whintson, frontiers person Education (Singapore)Pvt.Ltd. Indian Branch New Delhi.
- “E-Commerce” Electronic Payment system, Kamalesh K.Bajaj and Deljani Nag
- Banking theory law and practice,Garden and Arunkumar,Himalaya publishing house (2006).
- Electronic Commerce Kalarota and whintson, frontiers person Education (Singapore)Pvt.Ltd. Indian Branch New Delhi.
- “E-Commerce” Electronic Payment system, Kamalesh K.Bajaj and Deljani Nag